

Meta study of potential for PV installations in Switzerland

Matthias Hügi¹, Nicolas Wyrsh^{2,*}, Christof Bucher¹, Donat Hess¹, Christophe Ballif²

¹ Bern University of Applied Sciences (BFH), CH-3400 Burgdorf, Switzerland

² École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL), CH-2000 Neuchâtel, Switzerland

Abstract

Numerous studies have been conducted to evaluate the potential of photovoltaic systems in Switzerland, considering roofs, facades, infrastructure, or free land installations. These studies differ by the datasets used, their methods, the assumptions on the system performance, and the installation details, but more importantly, by the various reduction factors introduced to obtain a realistic estimate of the photovoltaic potential. The present study reviews the critical elements of these studies, especially for roofs and facades, and their influences on the potential value. The system integration and grid aspects are not taken into account. It is observed that the system performance alone, given mainly by the considered module efficiency, does not permit to unify the results. The details of the methods, especially in the case of the analysis based on machine-learning techniques and flat reductions to account for unsuitable or forbidden roofs or facades, are the main reasons for the discrepancies in the results. A potential of 50-60 TWh/a from roofs and 20 TWh/a from facades can be estimated from the most recent studies, while a minimum potential of more than 20 TWh/a from other surfaces (infrastructure, lakes, alpine and agrivoltaics) could be exploited. A conservative potential of 70 TWh/a is sufficient for the realisation of the Swiss Energy transition.

Glossary

Term	Meaning
PV	Photovoltaic
Agri-PV	Agrivoltaic or Agri-Photovoltaic
PR	Performance ratio
Roof 360°	Roofs without orientation restrictions
Roof south or +/-90°	Roofs with orientation from -90° to 90° azimuth

1 Introduction

Aiming at a net zero CO₂ emission by 2050, at the latest, is the goal of the Swiss energy transition (Energy Perspectives 2050+ [1]). To achieve these goals, several sectors need to switch to renewable energy sources or to be electrified. Among them, the main ones are buildings (space and domestic hot water heating) and mobility. In addition, heat and cold demands in the industry need to be renewables sourced and additional electricity production is also required due to the phase-out of the nuclear power stations. Depending on the various scenarios, an additional electricity production between 36 and 48 TWh/a will be needed till 2050 [1].

In this context, photovoltaic (PV) is one of the main renewable energy sources expected to fill the energy gap. Possible other renewable sources have limited potential or acceptance in the Swiss context. Additional hydro sources are limited due to the already extensive use of the existing resources. Due to relatively poor acceptance, wind energy has been extremely difficult to deploy in Switzerland. Biomass is an interesting source but rather expensive and difficult to scale up. Furthermore, its resources are limited and can only contribute to a minor share of the required

* Corresponding author: nicolas.wyrsh@epfl.ch

electricity production [2]. PV is thus the renewable source which offers the largest potential at the most competitive cost [3,4].

The growth of PV is global, taking a growing share of the renewable energy source and is expected to be the major source by 2050 [4]. For that reason, it deserves to be analysed in detail. The growth of PV in the energy mix has been driven by the rapid decrease in PV electricity costs. The latter is due to a sharp reduction in material costs, upscaling of the technology and improvements in solar cell efficiency. Solar cell efficiency has steadily increased over the years across all technologies (see Figure 1). The best monocrystalline cells, which are the most common type on the market, show a lab efficiency of more than 26 % [5]. By 2020 the total weighted average module efficiency of the crystalline Silicon cells was at 20.4 %, whereas the lowest monocrystalline module efficiency was 16.3 % and the highest at 22.4 % [6]. Considering the module efficiencies of modules entering the market in 2022, the weighted average is 20.55 %. It should be noted that this average is expected to continue to increase in the future [7], increasing the effective PV potential.

Figure 1: Development of solar cell efficiency over the years. Database: 2006-2016 → [8], 2017-2022 → [9]

The PV module price per watt has been reduced by a factor of 10 during the last decade [10], leading to the possibility of producing electricity below 2 €cts/kWh with large plants in sunny countries [11]. In central Europe and Switzerland, in less sunny countries, large PV plants can produce electricity at prices well below 10 €cts/kWh [3], and are competitive with other new sources of electricity.

Due to the scarcity of free land in Switzerland, PV systems should be installed mostly on buildings or existing infrastructure to meet public acceptance and keep installation costs acceptable. To discuss Swiss energy scenarios, it is therefore necessary to identify and quantify the potential of PV resources. In this context, several authors have analysed the energy production potential of Swiss roofs [12–26]. The potentials calculated in these analyses differ significantly, and it is thus essential to understand the reasons for the discrepancies. While these studies are based on the same basic set of data, namely the Swiss building registry, their methodology and assumptions differ. This paper aims, therefore, to compare the assumptions and methodologies and to quantify the related influence in the calculated potential. The purpose is here to harmonise the evaluation of the Swiss PV potential of roofs which could contribute to the transition to net zero carbon emission. For this evaluation, issues or limitations given by the grid capacity, operation or stability are not considered as they are assumed to be more financial than technical constraints. Furthermore, in the built-environment, a smart management of new flexible assets, given by the electrification of the mobility and building heating, is expected to mitigate the problem and allow

for a much higher share of PV with costly grid reinforcement. While other renewable sources could contribute to the Swiss energy transition, only the one from PV (expected to be the main one from new renewable sources) is discussed in this paper.

Historically, PV installations on roofs in Switzerland were incentivised by the introduction of a feed-in tariff first in Burgdorf in 2001, followed by a national scheme in 2009 [27]. Such a scheme has allowed the installation of approx. 2 GW_p of grid-connected PV. Since 2018, it has been replaced by a non-recurrent remuneration covering a share of the investment costs. Besides this one-time payment, financial incentives are mainly given by self-consumption. Driven by the increasing price of electricity, approx. 1.5 GW_p was added in 2023.

In addition to the potential of roofs, other contributions to the PV potential will also be discussed. Several studies report on the potential of facades [12,16,18,19,21], lakes [28], agrivoltaic or agri-PV [29,30], alpine regions [19,31–33] and other infrastructures [19,34–37]. For some of them, they could offer a relatively large contribution to the full PV potential but are also, in many cases, more controversial. The various types of PV installation and their main characteristics, the main database for building installations and the calculation method for their respective irradiation calculation will be presented in section 2. The specific methodology related to the present study and comparison of the existing studies will be detailed in Chapter 3.

Chapters 4 and 5 describe in detail the different studies, their methodology, main assumptions, and results, and discuss the main elements leading to the discrepancies. By quantifying the impact of the differences in the analysis, we aim to provide a much narrower range for the PV potential of rooftops and facades in Switzerland, to provide a comprehensive and more accurate value for the total PV potential, together with the other potential contributions (lakes, facades, agriculture and infrastructure).

2 Description of PV system types

PV systems can be classified in terms of their installation sites, geographical locations, mounting structures and connection to the grid. For the present study, we will focus on PV systems offering substantial potential for the coverage of the Swiss electrical consumption and briefly discuss their characteristics, limits, advantages, and prospective contribution to the electrification of the Swiss energy system. For this reason, only grid-connected systems will be presented and discussed below. A link to state-of-the-art or representative installations are eventually given below.

2.1 Roof

In Switzerland, given the high population density and scarce availability of free and accessible land, the constructed area and especially buildings offer the least conflict for distributed PV generation [38]. The total roof area for Switzerland usable for PV systems (large enough for a meaningful installation without considering orientation) is estimated at 440 km², 147 km² of them being flat roofs [24]. The latter thus offers a valuable potential for large PV systems. Historically, PV systems were mounted south-facing on flat roofs. The main reason was to maximise the production with a minimum number of modules, with PV modules representing the most expensive share of the installation costs. Rows of modules were separated by a certain distance to avoid shading of modules by adjacent ones [39]. With the decrease in module price, it is today much more economical to cover most of the flat roof surface with modules (usually installed east-/west-facing with a low tilt to favour dust cleaning by rain [39]). This installation maximises the production of PV over the year.

PV systems on tilted roofs represent another important potential for PV installation. As the module orientation is given by the roof orientation, only a fraction of the roof area is considered adequate. While east and west-facing oriented roofs produce less than a south-facing one, the difference in the yearly production for 45° tilt is minimal: an east- or west-facing module produces 75 % of a south-facing one). Installation on north-facing roofs with a low irradiance can also be economically attractive in some cases, especially for roofs with a low tilt angle.

2.2 Facade

The total surface of facades in Switzerland is estimated at 226 km² [19]. While the area is important, it is much more difficult to exploit than roofs. Facades usually offer few large free

surfaces without windows. For aesthetic reasons, they usually require building integration and dedicated facade elements including coloured or white PV modules. A picture of such a facade is shown in Figure 2. Other examples are presented in [40,41]. However, the addition of front textures and especially coloured foils or filters reduces the module efficiency; a maximal reduction of 40 % is exhibited by white modules [42]. Such a reduction in efficiency is not expected to reduce significantly the potential of facades as it allows the installation on buildings that could not be considered for aesthetic or protection reasons. Furthermore, facades in a built environment are more prone to shadowing by neighbouring buildings reducing the effective surface potential. However, a south facade with a 90° tilt of the module presents a maximum of the performance ratio (PR) in winter [43] and is, for this reason, important for filling the Swiss winter energy gap [44].

Figure 2: Example of a façade with white PV modules (demonstrator of EU project BE-Smart, picture N. Wyrsh)

2.3 Infrastructure

Switzerland offers a large-constructed surface beside buildings. A considerable potential for PV production is provided mainly by parking lots and sound barriers along rail tracks and highways. Several demonstration projects were carried out in Switzerland and Europe along highways [36]. The total area of parking lots, as identified in OpenStreetMap (excluding parking along roads and multi-storey ones), is 22.4 km². The Swiss Federal Roads is auctioning several highway sectors for building additional PV systems [45]. However, PV installations on infrastructure require dedicated mounting elements that can be more costly than installations on building roofs. Another specific case of installation on dams will be discussed below (section 2.7).

2.4 Solar Farms

Solar farms are the world's most important source of PV production and comprise the largest PV systems [46]. They require the availability of free land, ideally not used for agricultural purposes. While the first large-scale Swiss plant was built in 1991-1992 on Mt-Soleil as a solar farm with a power of 560 kW_p [47], the potential is limited in Switzerland as it competes with other land use [1]. However, there are possibilities where a dual use of the land is possible and allowed as in the case of Agri-PV (see section 2.5). Another case discussed in section 2.6 is that of alpine systems.

2.5 Agri-PV

The Swiss territorial organisation law amendment, in effect since 1 July 2022 [48], allows the possibility of building PV system on top of crop fields. Such agrivoltaic systems aim at benefiting from the combined effect of a PV system shading the crops for reducing too strong insulation and limiting plant transpiration and producing at the same time electricity [49]. Agrivoltaic systems are highly promising in hot and sunny countries but can also contribute, in the case of Switzerland, to contribute to the PV potential [50]. However, few studies have yet been conducted on the potential of Agri-PV. The assumptions these studies make about suitable areas also vary considerably and are based more on assumptions about social acceptance than technical potential.[51].

2.6 Alpine

As already mentioned, the transition to 100 % renewable energy will require producing more electricity in winter to fill the energy gap [38]. Given the meteorological situation of Switzerland, PV installations in the Alps (at altitudes above the fog) offer high winter production [38,52]. Such systems also benefit from the high albedo given by the snow coverage. Several systems have been recently constructed on dams to benefit from the existing electrical infrastructure or are in planning [53]. The construction of large solar farms in the Alps is now subsidised according to Energy Law 71 a. It offers a limited conflict with other land use but has limited acceptance due to the visual impact and constrained to the availability of the electric infrastructure for the connection point.

2.7 Lakes

Floating PV is attracting much attention in countries with limited land resources [54]. Lakes, seas or water reservoirs can be covered with large PV installations. In Switzerland, dams in the Alps are target situations for such types of PV systems. They have relatively low visual impact and exhibit high production in winter due to their situation at relatively high altitudes (see also previous section). A demonstration system with a yearly production of 800 MWh was recently constructed on the lac des Toules (at an altitude of 1810 m); it is to be extended for a production of 22 GWh [55].

In case of lakes, Agri-PV and infrastructure, the political framework conditions play a major role. These are currently being discussed in the political arena.

3 Methodology

3.1 Description of the used databases

Sonnendach.ch and Sonnenfassade.ch [56] are the websites of the Swiss Federal Office of Energy that include a database of all roof areas. For many buildings, the roof is divided into multiple data entries, but for practical purposes, they are combined into one PV system. To calculate how much solar power or heat a house's roof or facades could produce, they simulate the sun's path over the year to calculate the total incident solar radiation. Therefore, the building data siwssBUILDING3D 2.0 from *Swisstopo* and geodata are used to calculate the area, slope and orientation for each roof/facade. The irradiation, respectively, shading effects, of buildings, vegetation and topography are calculated using Perez models and subsequently categorised.

Roof:

Description	Dependence on mean annual irradiation
Low	< 800 kWh/m ² /a
Medium	≥ 800 and < 1000 kWh/m ² /a
Good	≥ 1000 and < 1200 kWh/m ² /a
Very good	≥ 1200 and < 1400 kWh/m ² /a
Excellent	≥ 1400 kWh/m ² /a

Table 1: Categories in Sonnendach.ch for roofs [56]

Facades:

Description	Dependence on mean annual irradiation
Low	< 600 kWh/m ² /a
Medium	≥ 600 and < 800 kWh/m ² /a
Good	≥ 800 and < 1000 kWh/m ² /a
Very good	≥ 1000 and < 1200 kWh/m ² /a
Excellent	≥ 1200 kWh/m ² /a

Table 2: Categories in Sonnenfassade.ch for facades [56]

The value of the total incident solar radiation is then further used to calculate the total electricity yield by multiplying with the module efficiency and the performance ratio (PR) (Eq. 1 below and discussion in section 3.3). Those two values are defined to be 17 % for the module efficiency and 80 % for the performance ratio [18,56].

$$\text{Total electricity yield} = \text{total incident solar radiation} * \text{PR} * \text{module efficiency} \quad (1)$$

3.2 Reduced set of roofs and facades

Many studies exclude some of the roofs and facades listed in Sonnendach.ch. A reduced set, called in the following “reduced Sonnendach” does not consider roof areas <10 m² and irradiation categories "medium" and "low" for roofs (see Table 1). In the case of facades, areas <20 m² and irradiation category "low" are excluded (see Table 2) [56].

3.3 Procedure for creating this study

The methodology used in this meta-study is the following:

- 1) All studies on the PV potential in Switzerland published between 1998 and 2023 have been collected.
- 2) The different assumptions, methods and results from these studies were extracted by the Bern University of Applied Sciences and EPFL.
- 3) All authors of the various studies were contacted and asked about a participation in this meta-study.
- 4) The extracted data of each study were sent to the respective authors for control/confirmation of accuracy.
- 5) All data from the studies were classified into different categories (rooftop, facades, ...) for comparison purposes.
- 6) Missing values (not explicitly indicated) to compare the studies were calculated/defined by the Bern University of Applied Sciences and EPFL. These values are marked (underlined) in the appendix and comprise.
 - a) Non-apparent base values of the studies such as
 - i) Performance ratio (not explicitly indicated in 9 out of 24 studies)
 - ii) System efficiency or module efficiency (not explicitly indicated in 6 out of 24 studies)
 - b) Additional values for further calculations such as
 - i) Conversion of system efficiency to module efficiency (or vice versa)
 - ii) Roof or facades area
 - iii) Potential steps between the initial potential and the resulting potential from the study
 - c) Resulting potential indication
 - i) Energy out of power (1 study)
- 7) The potentials of all studies were normalized to 20.55 % module efficiency.
- 8) The results were evaluated and are presented in graphs and discussed in the following chapters.

With the PR and the module efficiency, the system efficiency can be calculated (see Eq. 2). Note that the PR value includes all system losses, including temperature effect, inverter losses, line losses, soiling, snow coverage, etc. While all these effects can be modelled theoretically and

depend on module type and installation type, a fixed value is assumed for simplicity and easy comparisons [48]. It is expected to marginally affect the overall Swiss PV potential.

$$\text{System efficiency} = \text{Module efficiency} * PR \quad (2)$$

A value of 0.8 was assumed for the PR if it was not explicitly indicated in the study. Apart from one study, all those that defined it used a value of 0.8.

3.4 Division of roof areas

For the potential on roof surfaces, some studies limited the roof orientations that could be used. Thereby, north-facing roof surfaces were omitted from the beginning. These are referred to as "Roof south" in this study and only consider roofs within a range of orientation around south (+/- 45° or +/- 90° around south). Others basically allowed all roof orientations. These are called "Roof 360°" in this study.

4 Results

In this section, the PV potential of the different studies is presented graphically and compared in general with each other. The basis for this evaluation can be found in the appendix. Chapter 10.1 shows the assumptions and the results of the different studies, and Chapter 10.2 describes their methodology.

4.1 Roof and facades

Figure 3 compares different studies, each of them making statements about the same potential type but based on different assumptions. The different colours of the bars indicate which reductions are made from the initial potential (see Table 3). In the end, all studies result in a final potential in purple. Furthermore, all figures contain horizontal lines, which show the initial and reduced values of sonnendach.ch (as explained in section 3.1). The top two horizontal lines are based on data from the study by Portmann 2019 [18] coincide exactly with the bars of that study. The third (bottom) line in Figure 3 a) and b) marks the usable potential of 50 TWh/a for roofs, which was published by the federal government in 2018 [57]. The third line in Figure 3 c) marks the usable potential of 17 TWh/a for facades, as published by the federal government in 2019 [58].

Blue	Reduction due to areas and irradiation. This includes areas that are too small as well as areas with too little irradiation.
Red	Reduction due to disruptive objects. This includes areas that cannot be used due to existing objects such as chimneys, windows, doors and others.
Orange	Reduction due to reluctance to build. This includes whether a building owner is willing to install a PV system on his building in the near future.
Purple	This is the resulting PV potential of the respective study.

Table 3: Explanation of the different deductions from the total PV potential

Figure 3 a) compares studies that consider all roof orientations as described in Chapter 3.4. Due to their methodology, the first two studies and the last one do not indicate an initial potential and only show the resulting potential. The other seven studies are based on sonnendach.ch, so their unreduced values are all similar or even identical. Remund 2017 shows a slightly higher maximum PV potential because, at that time, Sonnendach.ch was not covering Switzerland entirely and necessitated an extrapolation. Anderegg 2022 has adopted Sonnendach.ch with a module efficiency of 20 % instead of 17 %, resulting in a higher value. However, some of the final potentials vary considerably. If only the resulting potentials are compared, it seems that Buffat 2017 and Portmann 2019 do not match the continuous increase in potential. However, if the reluctance to build is neglected, all studies since 2019 show between 38.8 and 55.2 TWh/a.

In Figure 3 b), studies using only south-facing roofs are contemplated, see Chapter 3.4. The final potentials are, therefore, somewhat lower than the potential for all roof orientations. Only Cattin 2012 [13] shows a higher total potential, which is then reduced by considering various factors. This graph shows a continuous increase in the PV potential over the years.

Figure 3.c) compares five studies, four of which are based on data from sonnenfassade.ch. Gutschner 2002 [12] does not perform a step-by-step reduction. The values from Portmann 2019 [18] clearly turn out to be the highest, although it should be mentioned that no reduction was made for reluctance to build. Also here, Remund 2017 [16] refers to the extrapolation of Sonnendach.ch.

Figure 3: Comparison of PV potential studies for roof (a,b) and facades (c)

4.2 Roof and facades normalised

Since most studies assume different efficiencies of the solar modules, their final potential was corrected and presented in Figure 4 (corresponding to the studies in Figure 3). The module efficiency was normalised to 20.55 %¹. That leads, with a PR of 80 %, to an overall system efficiency of 16.44 %. Through this procedure, the potentials can be better compared. However, the ratios of the potentials to each other do not change much. Therefore, the differences are not due to the different module efficiencies.

¹ Average PV module efficiency from the California Energy Commission database [59] for the year 2022.

Figure 4: Comparison of PV potential studies for roofs and facades considering the same solar module efficiency of 20.55 %.

4.3 Other locations

Figure 5 shows the potential for locations other buildings or sites. The potential for agri-PV is clearly the largest with 132 TWh/a or 323 TWh/a. The resulting alpine potential varies by more than a factor of 8 between the different studies if the reductions are not considered. Among the other sites, the potentials along roads and on reservoirs/dams are the most important. The others have a low potential. It is important to note that these are individual studies for specific areas. In contrast to roofs and facades, there are usually not several different studies for these categories. Moreover, the potential of these categories has only recently been explored for the first time.

Figure 5: Comparison of PV potentials other locations

A list specifying the potential of “other sites” is detailed in Table 4. The latter also mentioned the related study (with author and year).

Other sites	Potential [TWh/a]	Study
Artificial lakes	0.60	Grüter 2021
Avalanche barriers	0.01	Grüter 2021
Balcony ²	0.70	Remund 2024
Dams	0.09	Grüter 2021
Reservoirs and dams ²	10.00	Remund 2022
Embankments	0.07	Grüter 2021
Free areas along roads	24.70	Remund 2019
Gravel and quarries	0.01	Grüter 2021
Landfills	0.01	Grüter 2021
Motorway embankments	5.60	Remund 2019
Motorway galleries	0.01	Grüter 2021
Motorway roofing	0.22	Grüter 2021
Noise protection walls along railway ³	0.05	Planair SA 2021
Noise protection walls along roads	0.80	Grüter 2021
Noise protection walls along roads	0.13	Nordmann 2012
Noise protection walls along roads	0.06	Planair SA 2021
Parking lot roofing	0.80	Grüter 2021
Parking lot roofing	4.90	Remund 2019
Parking lot roofing	2.89	Meier 2023
Substations	0.02	Grüter 2021
Train station roofing	0.08	Grüter 2021
Wastewater treatment plants	0.08	Grüter 2021

Table 4: More detailed consideration of the other sites regarding PV potential

4.4 Additional studies

Some studies do not consider rooftop potential but look at the possible PV demand. For example, they looked at how the nuclear phase-out could be compensated with renewable energy. These studies are listed below as a supplement and are not used for direct PV potential comparison:

- Bartlett et al. 2018 [44] 17.9 TWh/a Roof south
- Dujardin et al. 2021 [60] 25 TWh/a Roof south
- Kahl et al. 2019 [52] 12 TWh/a Alpine

Furthermore, some studies only look at parts of Switzerland. List is not exhaustive.

- Gutschner and Nowak 1998 a [61] City Zürich
- Gutschner and Nowak 1998 b [62] Canton Freiburg

² Remund 2022/2024 has not yet been officially published until 07.05.2024.

³ Planair: 46 GWh/a. The Swiss Railways reduced this value to 10 GWh/a on the basis of economic considerations.

- Scartezzini et al. 2002 [63] Urban
- NET Nowak Energie & Technologie AG 2004 [64] Canton Geneva
- M. Montavon et al. 2005 [65] Urban
- Gutschner 2006 [66] City Geneva
- Montavon 2010 [67] Urban
- Orehounig et al. 2014 [68] Village
- Mohajeri et al. 2016 [69] City Geneva
- Mohajeri et al. 2018 [70] Urban
- Bernasconi et al. 2020 [71] Canton Ticino
- Anderegg et al. 2021 [72] Canton Glarus
- Albrecht-Widler et al. 2021 [73] City Zürich

5 Discussion

The assumptions of each study can be found in Appendix 10.1 and 10.2. In this section, the results are analysed in more detail and put in context with the different assumptions of the studies to explain the differences. For buildings, three different categories can basically be assumed. Roofs without orientation restrictions (roof 360°), roofs with orientation from -90° to 90° azimuth (roof south) and facades.

5.1 Roof and facades

5.1.1 Roof 360°

For the studies that consider all orientations, it can be said that the assumptions made about the usable area have a great influence. The biggest uncertainties are not in the irradiation on the buildings, but other assumptions such as whether the will to build is considered or not.

Gutschner's study [12] shows a lower potential than the other studies. One reason is the lower system efficiency, which was only about 50 % of today's numbers. In addition, thin-film technology was adopted because it was predicted to have a large market share. Gutschner 2002 [12] and Buffat 2017 [15] consider a system efficiency of only 10 % (which corresponds to a module efficiency of 13 % and a PR of 80 %). The other studies assume 13.6 % (module efficiency 17 % and PR 80 %). Gutschner 2002 [12] calculated the roof area as 120 % of the building footprint. Compared to Gutschner, Buffat shows a much larger total potential. Nevertheless, this is only about half as large as in the other studies. Buffat assumes that the building footprint corresponds to the area of the roof. However, it does not explicitly include a reduction for interfering roof structures.

Remund 2017 [16] used Sonnendach.ch as the basis for the potential calculation, but it was not complete at that time. The extrapolation of the total potential leads with 100.5 TWh/a to a slightly higher total potential than finally shown in the complete Sonnendach.ch database. From 2019, all studies that use Sonnendach.ch are based on the complete database.

Reduction due to areas/irradiation:

As of 2017, a deduction for minimum areas and minimum irradiation was applied to the studies. This deduction varies depending on the study. While Rohrer 2020 [20] / Remund 2020 [21] / Moro 2021 [23] used the same reduction as Portman 2019 [18], i.e. areas <10 m² and irradiations of the category "low" and "medium" according to Klauser 2016 [56] were omitted ("reduced Sonnendach"), Remund 2017 [16] / Remund 2019 [19] / Anderegg 2022 [24] made a larger deduction. Remund 2017 [16] used a reduction factor of 51.2 % for the area according to Portmann 2016 [74]. Remund 2019 [19] reduced the area overall by 30 %, and Anderegg 2022 excluded flat roofs <50 m² in addition to "reduced Sonnendach" (resulting in a reduction of 24.7 %). Buffat 2017 [15] removed areas with lower irradiation than 1000 kWh/m²/a from the total potential (this corresponds in principle to the reduction according to Klauser 2016 [56]). This results in a reduction of 22 %. Walch 2023 [26] excludes all areas <8 m².

In Remund 2017 [16], the resulting potential comes from the intersection of economic, ecological/cultural-historical and social potential. The exact procedure is not apparent. Among other things, objects worthy of protection are also excluded.

Reduction due to disruptive objects:

Reductions due to disruptive roof elements were made in studies based on Sonnendach. For Portmann 2019 [18], a flat reduction of 30 % is applied for roofs with a pitch $>10^\circ$. For roofs with a pitch $<10^\circ$, the reduction varies between 20 % and 58 % depending on the building type. Overall, this results in a reduction of 35.7 %. Remund 2019 / 2020 [19,21] assumes a flat reduction of 29 % according to calculations considering Portmann 2016 [74] (incl. 5 % for objects worthy of protection). Rohrer 2020 [20], like Remund 2019 [19], assumes that 5 % are objects worthy of protection and 32 % of the roof areas cannot be used due to extensions. The overall reduction is, therefore, 35 %. Moro 2021 [23] calculated the proportion of disturbing superstructures using randomly selected roofs in Zurich and arrived at a reduction factor of 50 %. Anderegg 2022 [24] examined 7 roof categories, each with as many roofs as required to fall below a predefined standard error of the mean and concluded that 40 % cannot be used.

Reduction due to reluctance to build:

Remund 2019 / 2020 [19,21] and Rohrer 2020 [20] additionally assumed that 52.5 % of the remaining potential cannot be used because there are reservations about building a PV system.

5.1.2 Roof south

When considering only south-facing roofs, it is obvious that the values are much lower than in the studies considering all roof orientations, as fewer roof areas are usable. All studies consider the azimuth angle from -90° to 90° (“+/- 90° south” as mentioned in the Appendix).

System efficiency:

Cattin 2012 [13] assumes a system efficiency of 12.75 % (module efficiency 15 %, PR 85 %). The others use 13.6 % (module efficiency 17 %, PR 80 %).

Minimum areas:

Cattin 2012 [13] do not specify the minimum roof area used. Assoulin 2016 [14] only considers roof areas of at least 28 m², while Assouline 2018 [17] considers all areas >5 m². Walch 2020 / 2022 [22,25] includes all areas >8 m². Compared to the assumptions in Sonnendach.ch (areas >10 m²), Assouline 2016 [14] excludes many potential areas from the beginning (especially non-south oriented roofs), the other three studies include some smaller roof areas. Assouline 2016 [14] shows that only 81 % roof area is available compared to the building footprint. This is about 20 % less than assumed by Buffat 2017 [15].

Methods:

Most of these studies after 2016 are based on machine learning (ML) algorithms. The range of potential varies as the different studies are based on different irradiation models and different ML-Models to estimate the potential area, and the shading calculations are not the same either. The difference from Assouline 2016 [14] to Assouline 2018 [17] is small and probably due to the change from the ML algorithm SVM to Random Forest, leading to different potential areas. Also, the difference from Walch 2020 [22] to Walch 2022 [25] is most likely due to further development of the ML algorithms.

5.1.3 Facades

Looking at all five studies considering the PV potential on facades a wide range from 3.4 TWh/a up to 16.9 TWh/a is observable. Gutschner 2002 [12] assumes a system efficiency of only 10 %, as with the potential on roofs, and calculated the facade area as 150 % of the building footprint.

Reduction due to areas/irradiation:

The value from Remund 2017 [16] is lower as the reduction for area and irradiance are much bigger, 80 %, compared to the following facades studies. Portmann 2019 [18] and Remund 2020 [21] have used a reduction of 42 %. This corresponds to the “reduced Sonnendach” and excludes facade areas <20 m² and areas with irradiation “low”. For Remund 2019 [19], a flat deduction of 45 % was made.

The reductions of areas and irradiation for Remund 2017 [16] facades are identical to those for the roofs. It is an intersection of economic, ecological/cultural-historical and social potential, but the procedure is not precisely specified. Objects worthy of protection are also excluded.

Reduction due to disruptive objects:

In Remund 2019 / 2020 [19,21], an additional 45 % of the potential area was discarded at a flat rate due to interfering objects (such as windows, doors, etc.). For Portmann 2019 [18], the reduction is between 45 % and 60 % depending on the building type. On the existing building stock, this results in a total reduction of 49 %.

Reduction due to the reluctance to build:

Only Remund 2019 / 2020 [19,21] has made a deduction of 52.5 % for the reluctance to build, as with the roof potential.

5.2 Other sites

5.2.1 Alpine

When looking at the different alpine potentials, large differences can be observed. The study by Schwarz (Egli) 2022 [75] and De Ferrars 2023 [33] shows values of 41 TWh/a and 55.7 TWh/a respectively, which is a multiple of Remund 2019 [19] (16.4 TWh/a). Remund 2019 [19] restrict the range stronger and only consider areas between 1500 and 2500 m.a.s.l, whereas Schwarz 2022 [75] consider altitudes from 800 to 2700 m.a.s.l and De Ferrars 2023 [33] all over 1500 m.a.s.l. Further, the coverage in Remund 2019 [19] is only 35 %. The latest study by Meyer 2023 [32] divides the potential into three different groups (total potential / realisable potential / target potential). The system efficiency is not specified for Meyer 2023 and De Ferrars 2023. For Remund 2019 [19] it is 13.6 % and for Schwarz 2022 [75] 15 %. All these differences probably lead to these large differences.

5.2.2 Diverse sites

For the potential on lakes, it is assumed that 5 % of the total area of lakes in Switzerland can be used for PV and this results in 15 TWh [76]. For agri-PV the 2022 study shows potential of 131.9 TWh/a, which is more than all potential roofs and facades together. However, the usable potential of the three main categories differs significantly. Open arable land: 93.3 TWh/a, permanent green: 33.5 TWh/a and permanent crops: 5.1 TWh/a [29]. The new study from 2024 increases the potential to 323 TWh/a. The reason for this is more precise data sources for irradiation [30]. Also, other infrastructures such as parking lots or on noise protections along roads or rail ways have a notable potential. However, the potentials of the few comparable estimates differ widely in some cases, and no clear figure can be determined.

5.3 Normalisation of module efficiency

One initial hypothesis for the differences was that the different module efficiencies have an impact on the resulting potential. Considering Figure 4 a), the normalisation to a module efficiency of 20.55 % is not leading to a homogenisation of the potentials. Therefore, the discrepancies cannot be retraced to the different module efficiencies. The reason is much more likely to be found in the calculated areas, which are based on different assumptions as mentioned above. If the potentials are normalised to the areas, the values are much more homogeneous, as demonstrated by the similar results reported by most of the studies using Sonnendach.ch when no reduction related to the absence of willingness is applied.

In general, a higher module efficiency than 20.55 % would have to be assumed for the consideration of the medium-term potential, since with the exponential growth of the PV industry, the average efficiency will always be only slightly below the average of the newly added modules.

6 Conclusions

Numerous studies have been published worldwide on the PV potential on roofs and facades. Regarding the specific case of Switzerland, the largely different potentials reported by these studies were analysed in detail. Considering the evolution of the PV system efficiency does not lead to a harmonisation of the results. The main differences can be attributed to the specific assumptions made in those studies related to the detail of the installation (share of the roof that can be covered and orientation of the modules) as well as the type of the roof considered (roof orientation and minimal size). If all assumptions are harmonised, the potential should converge to similar potential values. Note that a precise validation of such a statement would be time consuming as several studies relies on the scale-up of limited size case studies or on machine leaning methods.

Several of the most recent studies also consider behavioural aspects with the reluctance of building owners to install PV systems. While this consideration leads to a strong reduction in the potential, both the magnitude of the reduction due to this consideration as well as the potential before taking it into account are quite similar. Regarding the relevance of this reduced potential, we should stress that this is not due to a physical limitation and can probably be removed by appropriate policies combining incentives and obligations.

We think the realistic potential is in the range of 50-60 TWh/a on rooftops of buildings, as this has been shown by the vast majorities of the studies. Those studies who show potentials below these values did either not have access to the building surface information [12] or they assumed that large shares of rooftops are not suitable for PV [17]. Current installation practices show that also roof areas which are excluded in those potential studies are being used for PV installations today. This is especially true for east or west-oriented rooftops. The PV potential on facades is estimated to be around 20 TWh/a. This estimate is subject to greater uncertainties because architectural restrictions and the limitation of use (e.g. due to windows) make a precise estimate difficult. However, due to low current building renovation rate of the Swiss stock of 0.82 %/year [73], the full use of the PV potential on rooftops is challenging. Building PV systems not on rooftops and facades only will increase the chance to realise the targeted amount of PV systems in Switzerland.

Conservatively, the potential on roofs and facades together adds up to about 70 TWh/a, which is sufficient for the realisation of the Swiss energy strategy. However, for a successful energy transition, it is important to that the roofs should be fully covered, as only partially covered roofs can be seen as a “PV potential killer” [24]. It is expected that any PV installation on a roof will not be modified with the lifetime of the PV modules and this fact will therefore strongly limits the achievable potential. Non-optimally used roofs may therefore critically affect medium-term targets of PV installed capacity. Additional incentives should be proposed to fully cover the roof area [77].

In addition to roofs and facades, significant additional potential has been identified by several studies on agricultural land, alpine land, lakes and other infrastructures. While the use of the latter should not lead to acceptance issues, installations in not-constructed areas or on free lands are critical and their actual potential is highly uncertain. Nevertheless, it can be helpful to reach the goal of the Swiss energy strategy and, especially for the case of alpine PV, provide much needed “winter electricity”. Considering all possibilities to deploy PV systems should also speed up considerably the pace of the energy transition and reduce risks and bottlenecks.

7 Contributors

The following persons, authors of the studies cited in this paper, contributed to the present meta-study by reviewing the assumptions and main findings of their studies, the discussion and the conclusion of this paper. These authors of the latter acknowledge their very important contributions.

Alina Ursula Rosa Walch	École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL)
Annellen Kahl	WSL-Institut für Schnee- und Lawinenforschung (SLF), EPFL

Christoph Koller	Zürcher Hochschule für Angewandte Wissenschaften (ZHAW)
Daniel Klauser	Meteotest AG
Daniel Ruoss	Enecolo AG
David Galvagno-Erny	e4plus AG
David Stickelberger	Swissolar
Dionis Anderegg	Zürcher Hochschule für Angewandte Wissenschaften (ZHAW)
Florian Egli	Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich (ETHZ)
Jan Remund	Meteotest AG
Jean-Louis Scartezzini	École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL)
Jérôme Dujardin	Institut SLF (WSL), École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL)
Jürg Rohrer	Zürcher Hochschule für Angewandte Wissenschaften (ZHAW)
Lars Konersmann	Energie Zukunft Schweiz AG (EZS)
Lucia Grüter	Energie Zukunft Schweiz AG (EZS)
Manuel Hunziker	Zürcher Hochschule für Angewandte Wissenschaften (ZHAW)
Marcel Gutschner	NET Nowak Energie & Technologie AG
Marius Schwarz	Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich (ETHZ)
Markus Portmann	e4plus AG
Martin Raubal	Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich (ETHZ)
Michael Lehning	WSL-Institut für Schnee- und Lawinenforschung (SLF), EPFL
Muriel Siegwart	Zürcher Hochschule für Angewandte Wissenschaften (ZHAW)
Nahid Mohajeri	École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL), University of Oxford
Niccolò Moro	Zürcher Hochschule für Angewandte Wissenschaften (ZHAW)
Nicolas Stocker	Zürcher Hochschule für Angewandte Wissenschaften (ZHAW)
Pedro Manso	École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL)
Peter Toggweiler	Basler & Hofmann AG
Priska Lorenz	e4plus AG
Ralph Lingel	TNC Consulting AG
Raphaël Compagnon	Hochschule für Technik und Architektur Freiburg (HTA-FR)
René Buffat	Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich (ETHZ)
Roberto Castello	École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL)
Sandra Probst	Energie Zukunft Schweiz AG (EZS)
Stefan Nowak	NET Nowak Energie & Technologie AG
Stefano Grassi	Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich (ETHZ)
Stuart Bartlett	École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL), Institut SLF (WSL)
Sven Strebel	Zürcher Hochschule für Angewandte Wissenschaften (ZHAW)
Thomas Nordmann	TNC Consulting AG
Thomas Vontobel	TNC Consulting AG
Varun Sharma	SUNWELL SARL

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10 Appendix

10.1 List of Studies

Missing values are calculated by BFH/EPFL. These values are underlined in the following table.

Name	Author	Title	Assumptions	Findings
Gutschner et al. 2002 [12]	Marcel Gutschner Stefan Nowak Daniel Ruoss Peter Toggweiler Tony Schoen	Potential for Building Integrated Photovoltaics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> System efficiency: 10 % / PR: <u>80 %</u> Roof area: 120 %, Facades area 150 % of ground floor 60 % of roof / 20 % of facades surface usable architecturally suitable 55 % of this roof and 50 % of this facades surface see at least 80 % of the maximum possible solar irradiation Suitable part roof: 40 % of ground floor Suitable part of facade: 15 % of ground floor Suitable part roof: 33 % of whole roof area Suitable part of facade: 10 % of whole facade area 	<p>Rooftop: 15.04 TWh/a (138.2 km²) Facade: 3.37 TWh/a (51.8 km²) 10 m² / Person roof with high solar yield Per 10 m² roof surface 1000 kWh/a production 100 m² ground surface = 40 m² roof + 15 m² facade</p>
Cattin et al. 2012 [13]	René Cattin Beat Schaffner Tanja Humar-Mägli Simon Albrecht-Widler Jan Remund Jürg J. Engel Daniel Klauser	Energiestrategie 2050 - Berechnung der Energiepotenziale für Wind- und Sonnenenergie	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PV module efficiency: 15 % (20 %) / PR: 85 % Orientation +/- 90° south (50 % reduction of total potential) Buildings >1000 m²: 80 % flat, 20 % pitched roofs/Buildings <1000 m²: 40 % flat, 60 % pitched roofs Flat roof: 50 % is used / Pitched roof: 100 % is used (2 m² per person reserved for solar heating) Disturbing elements: for buildings >1000 m² 20 %, for buildings <1000 m² 50 % of the area are not considered 5 % deduction of the area due to objects worthy of protection On buildings >1000 m² 60 % will be built on, <1000 m² 40 % will be built on 	<p>Sustainable potential (intersection of economical., ecological and social potential) Rooftop: 11.6 TWh/a @ 15 % efficiency (79 km²) Rooftop: 15.5 TWh/a @ 20 % efficiency (79 km²)</p>

Name	Author	Title	Assumptions	Findings
Nordmann et al. 2012 [34]	Thomas Nordmann Thomas Vontobel Ralph Lingel	Potential von Photovoltaik an Schallschutzmassnahmen entlang der Nationalstrassen	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PV module efficiency: 20 % (theoretical), 16 % (technical) / PR: 80 % • Min. distance from the ground: 0 m (theoretical), 1 m (technical), horizontal 1 m • Module inclination 45° • Module width: 0.2 m (theoretical), 1 m (technical), bifacial 1.6 m (theoretical), 1 m (technical) • Permitted total width: max. 2.5 m (theoretical), 2 m (technical) • Inverter efficiency 95 % 	<p>Noise protection wall:</p> <p>Theoretical: 410 GWh/a (2.2 Mio m²)</p> <p>Technical: 200-230 GWh/a (1.3-1.5 Mio m²)</p> <p>Realisable: 100-160 GWh/a (0.67-1 Mio m²)</p>
Assouline et al. 2016 [14]	Dan Assouline Nahid Mohajeri Jean-Louis Scartezzini	Quantifying rooftop photovoltaic solar energy potential: A machine learning approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PV module efficiency: 17 % / PR: 80 % • Orientation +/- 90° south • Roof area > 28 m² • 81 % of ground floor area is available for PV 	Rooftop: 17.86 TWh/a (328 km ²)
Buffat et al. 2017 [15]	René Buffat Stefano Grassi Martin Raubal	A scalable method for estimating rooftop solar irradiation potential over large regions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • System efficiency: 10.33 % / PR: 80 % • Yearly degradation rate of 0.9 % • PV estimated to have the same slope as the roof • Irradiation > 1000 W/m² • Orientation: -180° to 180° in 15° steps • Slope: 0° to 90° in 10° steps • Roof area and building footprint area 48'536 ha 	<p>Diagram for reading out different scenarios based on different irradiation and module efficiency.</p> <p>Rooftop: 53.2 TWh/a (41.3 TWh/a @ >1000 kWh/m²/a)</p>
Remund 2017 [16]	Jan Remund	Solarpotenzial Schweiz - Solarwärme und PV auf Dächern und Fassaden	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PV module efficiency: 17 % / PR: 80 % [56] • Roof area > 10 m² • Suitable roof "top", "very good", "good" [56] • 51.2 % of the roof areas are covered [74] • 20 % of the facades areas are covered • 47.5 % of the roofs/facades are sustainable usable (50 % reluctance to build and 5 % protected buildings) 	<p>Sustainable potential (intersection of economical, ecological and social potential)</p> <p>Rooftop: 24.6 TWh/a</p> <p>Facades: 5.6 TWh/a</p>
Assouline et al. 2018 [17]	Dan Assouline Nahid Mohajeri Jean-Louis Scartezzini	Large-scale rooftop solar photovoltaic technical potential estimation using Random Forests	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PV module efficiency: 17 % / PR: 80 % • Roof area > 5 m² • Orientation +/- 90° south 	Rooftop: 16.29 TWh/a (252 km ²)

Name	Author	Title	Assumptions	Findings
Bartlett et al. 2018 [44]	Stuart Bartlett Jérôme Dujardin Annellen Kahl Bert Kruyt Pedro Manso Michael Lehning	Charting the course: A possible route to a fully renewable Swiss power system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • System efficiency: 15 %⁴ / PR: 80 % • Orientation +/- 45° south • Electricity production computed for a panel tilt of 39° 	Rooftop: 17.9 TWh/a (84 km ²)
Portmann et al. 2019 [18]	Markus Portmann David Galvagno-Erny Priska Lorenz David Schacher Rolf Heinrich	Sonnendach.ch und Sonnenfassade.ch: Berechnung von Potenzialen in Gemeinden	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PV module efficiency: 17 % / PR: 80 % [56] • Roof area > 10 m², facades > 20 m² • Suitable roof "top", "very good", "good" [56] • Facades that fall short of the minimum distance (100-200 m) to sites worthy of protection are not considered. • Roof areas are utilised to 70 % due to construction/technical restrictions (flat roofs slightly different) • Facade areas are utilised to 45 - 60 % (depending on the type of building), only building "single house", "high-rise» and "under construction" are considered. 	Rooftop: 50.0 TWh/a Facades: 16.9 TWh/a
Kahl et al. 2019 [52]	Annellen Kahl Jérôme Dujardin Michael Lehning	The bright side of PV production in snow-covered mountains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • System efficiency: 15 % / PR: 80 % • Tilt: 0°-90° 	Alpine: 12 TWh/a Needed area for 12 TWh depending on panel tilt from 45 up to 55 km ² with snow cover (up to 65 km ² without snow cover)

⁴ According to consultation with the authors, it was assumed in the study that the overall PV efficiency (System efficiency) is 15 %.

Name	Author	Title	Assumptions	Findings
Remund et al. 2019 [19]	Jan Remund Simon Albrecht-Widler David Stickelberger	Das Schweizer PV-Potenzial basierend auf jedem Gebäude	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PV module efficiency: 17 % / PR: 80 % [56] • 30 % reduction of the roofs • 45 % reduction of the facades • 29 % of the roof areas are covered • 45 % of the facades areas are covered (5 % of the roof/facades areas are protected [13]) • 50 % of roofs / facades are not immediately realisable (medium-term) • Free areas-have a reduction of 25 - 99 % (medium-term) • Alpine plants: tilt 70°, azimuth 0°, Coverage rate is 35 %, >100 kWh/m²/a, 1500-2500 m.a.s.l., 3°-28° inclination of terrain, without protected areas, with road connection 	<p>Rooftop: 49.1 TWh/a (medium-term 23.3 TWh/a)</p> <p>Facades: 17.2 TWh/a (8.2 TWh/a)</p> <p>Roads: 24.7 TWh/a (2.5 TWh/a)</p> <p>Parking slots: 4.9 TWh/a (3.9 TWh/a)</p> <p>Along motor ways: 5.6 TWh/a (3.9 TWh/a)</p> <p>Alps ground mounted: 16.4 TWh/a (3.3 TWh/a)</p>
Walch et al. 2020 [22]	Alina Ursula Rosa Walch Roberto Castello Nahid Mohajeri Jean-Louis Scartezzini	Big data mining for the estimation of hourly rooftop photovoltaic potential and its uncertainty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PV module efficiency: 17 % / PR: 80 % • Roof area > 8 m² • Orientation +/- 90° south and flat • Simulated PV panels of 1.6 m² on all roof geometries 	<p>Rooftop: 24.6 ± 9 TWh/a</p> <p>Area for PV: 267 ± 71 km²</p> <p>56.4 % of the total Swiss roof surface is available for the installation of PV</p>
Rohrer 2020 [20]	Jürg Rohrer	Ausbau der Stromproduktion aus Photovoltaik in der Schweiz	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PV module efficiency: 17 % / PR: 80 % [56] • Roof area > 10 m², facades > 20 m² • Suitable roof "top", "very good", "good" [56] • 5 % of the roof / facades areas are protected • 32 % of the roof areas are covered 	<p>Rooftop: 50.30 TWh/a (23.9 TWh/a incl. reluctance to build)</p>
Remund 2020 [21]	Jan Remund	Detailanalyse des Solarpotenzials auf Dächern und Fassaden	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PV module efficiency: 17 % / PR: 80 % [56] • Roof area > 10 m², facades > 20 m² • Suitable roof "top", "very good", "good" [56] • Suitable facade "top", "very good", "good", "medium" [56] • 29 % of the roof areas are covered • 45 % of the facades areas are covered (5 % of the roof/facades areas are protected [13]) • 50 % of roofs / facades are not immediately realisable (medium-term) 	<p>Rooftop: 55 TWh/a (medium-term 26.2 TWh/a)</p> <p>Facades: 18 TWh/a (9 TWh/a)</p>

Name	Author	Title	Assumptions	Findings
Grüter et al. 2021 [35]	Lucia Grüter Sandra Probst Lars Konersmann	Solarstrom auf Infrastrukturanlagen und Konversionsflächen	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>PV module efficiency: 17 % / PR: 80 %</u> • Noise barrier road: 2.2 Mio m² • Noise barrier railway: 250 km • Freeway roofing: 1544 km / 4069 ha • Highway galleries: 151 pieces of different length • Embankment railway: 3300 ha • Embankment road: 9700 ha • Parking lot roofing: 6400 ha • Track/perron roofing: 110'000 m² + 1490 x 750 m² • Dam: 677 pieces • Artificial lakes seen: 80 km² (30 largest lakes) • Wastewater treatment plants: ca. 800 pieces • Avalanche barriers: 600 km • Substations: 825 (electricity grid operator) + 60 (Railway), 1/3 usable with 200 kW • Landfills: 300 pieces • Gravel and quarries: 404 ha 	<p>Calculation of BFH/EPFL with 1000 kWh/kWp</p> <p><u>Noise barrier: 0.8 TWh/a</u></p> <p><u>Freeway roofing: 0.22 TWh/a</u></p> <p><u>Highway Galleries: 0.01 TWh/a</u></p> <p><u>Embankment: 0.07 TWh/a</u></p> <p><u>Parking lot roofing: 0.8 TWh/a</u></p> <p><u>Track/perron roofing: 0.08 TWh/a</u></p> <p><u>Dam: 0.09 TWh/a</u></p> <p><u>Artificial lakes: 0.6 TWh/a</u></p> <p><u>Wastewater treatment plants: 0.1 TWh/a</u></p> <p><u>Avalanche barriers: 0.002 TWh/a</u></p> <p><u>Substations: 0.02 TWh/a</u></p> <p><u>Landfills: 0.01 TWh/a</u></p> <p><u>Gravel and quarries: 0.01 TWh/a</u></p>
Planair SA 2021 [36]	Planair SA	Studie über das Potenzial der Lärmschutzwände entlang von Autobahnen und Bahnstrecken für die Produktion von Solarenergie	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>PV module efficiency: 17 % / PR: 80 %</u> • Towards road: tilt 60°, monofacial, horizontal • Away from road: tilt 30°, monofacial, vertical • On top (road): tilt 90°, bifacial, vertical • Away from railway or on top: tilt 30° • Minimal distance to the ground 1,1 m 	<p>Noise protection along national roads: 55 GWh/a (261 km)</p> <p>Noise protection along railway: 46 GWh/a (412 km)</p> <p>ASTRA facilities:</p> <p>Works yards: 24 GWh/a</p> <p>Galleries near tunnels: 6 GWh/a</p> <p>Galleries: 3 GWh/a</p> <p>Tunnel portals: 2 GWh/a</p> <p>Tunnel power plants: 0.6 GWh/a</p> <p>Other power plants: 0.2 GWh/a</p> <p>Total 36 GWh/a</p>
Moro et al. 2021 [23]	Niccolò Moro David Sauter Sven Strebel Jürg Rohrer	Das Schweizer Solarstrompotenzial auf Dächern	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PV module efficiency: (17 %) 20 % / PR: 80 % • Roof area > 10 m² • Suitable roof "top", "very good", "good" [56] • At least 3 adjacent modules 	<p>38.8 TWh/a @ 17 % efficiency (economical areas)</p> <p>45.6 TWh/a @ 20 % efficiency (economical areas)</p> <p>Roof area for PV: 231 km² (economical areas)</p> <p>44.8 TWh/a @ 17 % efficiency (all usable areas acc. sample)</p> <p>52.7 TWh/a @ 20 % efficiency (all usable areas acc. sample)</p> <p>Roof area for PV: 294 km² (all usable areas acc. sample)</p>

Name	Author	Title	Assumptions	Findings
Dujardin et al. 2021 [60]	Jérôme Dujardin Annellen Kahl Michael Lehning	Synergistic optimization of renewable energy installations through evolution strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Replace 29 TWh/a with renewables • Exclude northern orientations • 5 % of the constructed area can be covered with PV • Panels with a nominal capacity of 150 W/m² @ 20°C • < 500 m to next motorable road, < 2700 m.a.s.l • Exclude national parks 	Rooftop: 25 TWh/a in urban areas
Walch 2022 [25]	Alina Ursula Rosa Walch	Spatio-Temporal Estimation of Renewable Energy Potential in Built Environments using Big Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PV module efficiency: 17 % / PR: 80 % • Roof area > 8 m² • Orientation +/- 90° south • PV modules on flat roofs are south oriented 	Rooftop: 25 ± 9 TWh/a (standard assumptions) Roof area for PV: 267+/- 71 km ² Rooftop: 39 TWh/a (better module arrangement) Rooftop + BIPV: 60 TWh/a
Anderegg et al. 2022 [24]	Dionis Anderegg Sven Strebel Jürg Rohrer	Photovoltaik Potenzial auf Dachflächen in der Schweiz	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PV module efficiency: 17 % (20 %) / PR: 80 % • Steep roofs area > 20 m², flat roofs area > 50 m² • Suitable roof "top", "very good", "good" [56] • Module inclination and orientation according to roof geometry 	Rooftop: 45.6 ± 1.6 TWh/a @ 17 % efficiency Rooftop: 53.6 ± 1.9 TWh/a @ 20 % efficiency Total 644 km ² roofs, 440 km ² suitable for PV, of which 60 % is usable (264 km ² +/- 9 km ²)
Egli et al. 2022 [31] Tec. Capture: Schwarz 2022 [75]	Florian Egli Léonore Hälg Markus Schreiber Marius Schwarz (Lead author of the technical part)	Alpenstrom jetzt!	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • System efficiency: 15 % / PR: 80 % • Area > 5000 m² (~1 MWp) • 800 - 2700 m.a.s.l. • > 150 m away from a land slope > 30° • < 500 m to next road • Exclude national parks, unusable areas (glaciers, permanent snow covered), areas with northern orientation 	Alpine: 41 TWh/a (149.4 km ²)
Wanner et al. 2022 [28]	Aeneas Wanner Lucia Grüter Michael Arnold	Schwimmende Solarkrakerwerke auf Schweizer Seen	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PV module efficiency: 17 % / PR: 80 % • 5 % of lakes can be used 	Lakes: 15 TWh/a (1434.2 km ²)
Jäger et al. 2022 [29]	Mareike Jäger Christina Vaccaro Jürg Boos Johanna Junghardt Sven Strebel Dionis Anderegg Jürg Rohrer Beatrix Schibli	Machbarkeitsstudie Agri-Photovoltaik in der Schweizer Landwirtschaft	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PV modul efficiency: 19.55 % / PR: 80 % • PV modul efficiency bifacial: 30 % / PR: 80 % • 7 % more yield due to bifacial • Albedo: 20 % • Areas with irradiation >= 1000 kWh/m² 	Open arable land: 93.3 TWh/a (1339.4 km ²) Permanent green: 33.5 TWh/a (1168.9 km ²) Permanent crops: 5.1 TWh/a (61.5 km ²) Agri-PV: 131.9 TWh/a (2569.8 km ²)

Name	Author	Title	Assumptions	Findings
De Ferrars 2023 [33]	Desirée de Ferrars	The role of solar photovoltaics in the alps for the Swiss electricity system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PV module efficiency: 17 % / PR: 80 % • Orientation excludes north facing slopes • > 1500 m altitude • < 30° slope • < 100 m to next building, <500 m to next road • > 10 GWh, > 500 kWh/kWp • Exclude areas with risk of rockslide, non-suitable land, national parks, legally protected areas, avalanche risk areas 	Alpine: 57.7 TWh/a (350.66 km ²)
Meier 2023 [37]	Livio Meier	PV-Potenzial auf Parkplätzen in der Schweiz	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PV module efficiency: 20 % / PR: 80 % • Tilt: 0° • Using factor of parking lot area: 0.43 • Using factor of whole parking area: 0.90 	Parking lot roofing (only lots): 1.386 TWh/a Parking lot roofing (whole parking area): 2.887 TWh/a
Meyer et al. 2023 [32]	Lukas Meyer Anne-Kathrin Weber Jan Remund	Das Potenzial der alpinen PV-Anlagen in der Schweiz	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PV module efficiency: 17 % / PR: 80 % • Orientation south • Tilt: 90° 	Alpine: Total 104 TWh/a (1079 km ²) Realisable 45 TWh/a (464 km ²) Purposeful 5 TWh/a
Walch et al. 2023 [26]	Alina Walch Martin Rüdüsüli	Strategic PV expansion and its impact on regional electricity self-sufficiency: Case study of Switzerland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PV module efficiency: 17 % / PR: 80 % • Roof area > 8 m² • On flat surfaces are east/west-facing rows and tilt 15° • Roofs with a tilt angle below 10° are considered as flat • Simulated PV panels of 1.6 m² on all roof geometries 	Rooftop: 41.7 TWh/a
Anderegg et al. 2024 [30]	Dionis Anderegg Mareike Jäger Sven Strebel Jürg Rohrer	Potenzialabschätzungen für Agri-PV in der Schweizer Landwirtschaft	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Same as Jäger et al. 2022 [29] • Areas with irradiation ≥ 1000 kWh/m² 	Agri-PV: Theoretical total potential 323 TWh/a (5835 km ²) Open arable land: 225.3 TWh/a Permanent green: 84.6 TWh/a Permanent crops: 13.4 TWh/a @ <300m away from the road 113 TWh/a (2040 km ²) Open arable land: 92.2 TWh/a Permanent green: 33.5 TWh/a Permanent crops: 5.1 TWh/a

10.2 Methodology of the individual studies

10.2.1 Studies roof 360° and facades

Gutschner et al. 2002 [12]:

The ground floor area of the buildings is converted to roof and facade area. These, in turn, are subjected to further deductions based on architectural suitability and then offset against the irradiation. The factors were calculated by analysing representative samples with a limited number of buildings and sections of a given building stock, and then up scaling the results to the overall building stock. The basis was the area statistics with data from the 1990s. The potential roof area is assessed to 120 % and facades 150 % of ground floor. From this area only 60 % of roof and 20 % of facades surface is architecturally suitable. This value is further reduced as only 55 % of roof and 50 % of facade surface see at least 80 % of the maximum possible solar irradiation. This results in a suitable area of 33 % of the whole roof area and 10 % of the whole facade area. Which is the same as 40 % from the ground area for roofs and 15 % for facades.

Remund 2017 [16]:

The basis is sonnendach.ch (contains approx. 50 % of the buildings at this time). For the facade potential, the irradiations on facades were calculated (about 1/3 of the area of Switzerland was available at that time). This is the technical potential. The technical feasibility of roof and facades uses is determined with the help of the study by e4plus [74]. This study gives detailed deductions for the technical potential. The reduction is 51.2 %. At the end of this step results the economic potential. Subsequently, the data were extrapolated to the whole of Switzerland with the BAFU-study [13] and the help of a test area in the Mittelland for the facades. In addition to the economic potential, an "ecological/cultural-historical potential" and a "social potential" were also defined. The intersection of these three potentials results in the "sustainable potential".

Remund et al. 2019 [19]:

The theoretical potential of sonnendach.ch is reduced by reducing roof areas by a flat rate of 30 % and facade areas by a flat rate of 45 % (*Reduction area/irradiation*). Subsequently, a flat deduction of 29 % for roofs (calculated out of [74]) and 45 % for facades is made in order to exclude disturbing objects such as chimneys, windows, etc. (*Reduction disruptive objects*). Finally, the potential is reduced by 52.5 % to consider the reluctance to build and the protected objects (*Reduction reluctance to build*).

Portmann et al. 2019 [18]:

The theoretical potential of sonnendach.ch is reduced by omitting roof areas <10 m², facade areas <20 m², roof categories "low" and "medium" and facade categories "low" (*Reduction area/irradiation*). For roofs with a tilt >10° a flat rate reduction of 30 % is used. For tilts <10° the reduction varies from 20 % up to 58 % depending on the building type. For Facades the reduction depends on the building type as well and is between 45-60 % (*Reduction disruptive objects*). The resulting values are summed up at the end for each municipality.

Remund 2020 [21]:

The theoretical potential of sonnendach.ch is reduced by omitting roof areas <10 m², facade areas <20 m², roof categories "low" and "medium" and facade categories "low" (*Reduction area/irradiation*). Subsequently, a flat deduction of 29 % for roofs (calculated out of [74]) and 45 % for facades is made to exclude disturbing objects such as chimneys, windows, etc. (*Reduction disruptive objects*). Finally, the potential is reduced by 52.5 % to consider the reluctance to build and the protected objects (*Reduction reluctance to build*).

10.2.2 Studies only roof 360°

Buffat et al. 2017 [15]:

The Satellite Application Facility on Climate Monitoring (CM SAF) Surface Solar Radiation Data Set – Heliosat (SARAH) provides solar irradiance data. Monthly irradiance profiles are calculated from this with a half-hour time resolution. Thereby three scenarios are considered: long-term mean, monthly first quartile and monthly third quartile. In the second phase, intermediate datasets for orientations, slope and horizon angles are computed for each building. In the final third phase the

solar irradiation on rooftops is estimated. One result of this study is the cumulative solar energy on building roofs as a function of annual irradiation.

Rohrer 2020 [20]:

The theoretical potential of sonnendach.ch is reduced by omitting roof areas $<10 \text{ m}^2$ as well as roof categories "low" and "medium" (*Reduction area/irradiation*). Then, a standard deduction of 5 % is made for protected buildings and 32 % for disturbing objects such as chimneys, windows, etc. (*Reduction disruptive objects*). Finally, the potential is reduced by 52.5 % to consider the reluctance to build and the protected objects (*Reduction reluctance to build*).

Moro et al. 2021 [23]:

The theoretical potential of sonnendach.ch is reduced by omitting roof areas $<10 \text{ m}^2$ as well as roof categories "low" and "medium" (*Reduction area/irradiation*). To determine the reduction factors, 99 randomly selected roofs with a total of 690 partial roof areas in two neighbourhoods in the canton of Zurich were analysed. The roofs were covered with modules using the "K2 Base" design tool. The reduction factors could be determined based on this allocation and the effective roof size. It showed that the reduction factor is 39 % for flat roofs and 56 % for sloped roofs. Considering the proportions of flat roofs/sloping roofs, the reduction factor for usable areas is 50 % over all (*Reduction disruptive objects*).

Anderegg et al. 2022 [24]:

The theoretical potential of sonnendach.ch is reduced by omitting steep roof areas $<20 \text{ m}^2$ and flat roof area $<50 \text{ m}^2$ as well as roof categories "low" and "medium" (*Reduction area/irradiation*). To determine the reduction factors, seven categories of roofs were formed, and 120 random buildings in Switzerland were selected in each category. The roofs were occupied with modules using the SOLARAPP occupancy tool until an accuracy of 5 % was achieved. The reduction factors were determined based on this allocation and the effective roof size. Considering the proportions of flat roofs/sloping roofs, the total reduction factor for the usable areas is 60 % (*Reduction disruptive objects*).

Walch et al. 2023 [26]:

The hourly PV generation profiles are adapted from the existing study of Walch et al. [22]. It is estimated for all existing roofs in Switzerland (building reference year 2018). The primary inputs are a dataset of rooftop geometries for Switzerland from Klauser [56], as well as recorded solar radiation data from satellites for 2004-2015 as average monthly-mean-hourly (MMH) profiles. These MMH profiles contain one long-term mean hourly curve (24 h) for each month. The stochasticity of solar radiation is also taken into account. Based on the hourly PV generation profiles, it is classified the suitability of the roofs for PV installation. This classification provides insights into which roof types are most relevant for different PV expansion scenarios. In this study, the suitability of rooftops is based on their specific annual PV yield, which accounts for both the solar irradiation and the available area for PV installation. The total roof area does not only include roof parts eligible for PV installations, but also superstructures such as dormers, chimneys and other areas that are unsuitable for PV panels.

10.2.3 Studies only roof south

Cattin et al. 2012 [13]:

Using the solar radiation map of Switzerland from Meteotest 2012 and the total building area from the swissBuildings3D dataset, the total potential on buildings is calculated. This corresponds to the technical potential. Of this potential, 50 % of the pitched roofs are neglected. This emerges from studies in the city of Bern (Meteotest). In addition, 20 % of the areas on buildings $>1000 \text{ m}^2$ and 50 % of the areas on buildings $<1000 \text{ m}^2$ are omitted due to disturbing superstructures (economic potential). In addition to the economic potential, an "ecological/cultural-historical potential" and a "social potential" were also defined. The intersection of these three potentials results in the "sustainable potential".

Assouline et al. 2016 [14]:

The physical potential is based on the assessment of the total energy received from the sun by the urban areas. The monthly and yearly solar estimation is based on the existing satellite solar data

[78] and weather data (sunshine duration, temperature, precipitation, and cloud cover) from MeteoSwiss. This results in a raster map. Extrapolations for weather and insolation on surfaces were performed using support vector regression (SVR). The geographic or urban potential reflects the constraints on the locations where the solar energy can be captured and used for PV installations. Based on 42 municipalities in Geneva, areas for PV, shading and other elements on roofs are identified. In addition, the location, slope, orientation, and altitude are considered. SVR is then used to extrapolate to the whole of Switzerland. This results in an available area for PV of 81 % of ground floor area. The technical potential relates to the transformation of the solar energy received by the available roof area into electrical energy using the technical characteristics of the PV technology (e.g. efficiency and the performance).

Assouline et al. 2018 [17]:

The theoretical or physical potential is the total amount of received energy from solar energy. This is generated for using various datasets (SwissBuilding3D, Sonnendach, Roofdata, etc.) and the Random Forest method (RF) for the whole Switzerland. The urban or geographical potential is the physical potential restricted to areas suitable for PV production (tilted rooftops where PV panels can be installed). To extract this potential, the computation of the available area for PV installation over the roofs, the shadowing effects from surrounding obstacles, the roofs geometry characteristics, and finally the global radiation over tilted rooftops (combining horizontal radiations, roof geometric and shading effects) is necessary. The technical potential is the geographical potential reduced by the technical losses resulting from the PV panels. To determine the realistic potential, the socio-economic and market potential must also be determined.

Walch et al. 2020 [22]:

The solar radiation and albedo data is derived from Meteosat Second Generation (MSG) satellite observations using the Heliomont algorithm (2004-2015). The computation of the roof potential is based on a national dataset of building roofs in Switzerland's 3D building cadastre (LOD 2) with the roof tilt, aspect and area. This dataset is combined with the national register of buildings and dwellings (RBD), which gives information on the building's footprint, construction period, number of floors and building type. To account for obstructing objects on rooftops (superstructures), which impede the installation of PV panels, it is used a dataset derived from detailed city GML data (LOD 4) available only in the Canton of Geneva. It contains vector polygons that represent superstructures such as dormers and chimneys and covers nearly 38,000 roofs. The methodology combines this GIS, solar models and ML algorithm Random Forests to estimate the potential.

Walch 2022 [25]:

To estimate the rooftop potential and its uncertainty, the study proposes a methodology that combines Machine Learning, GIS processing and physical models for the treatment of large spatiotemporal datasets. Uncertainties are quantified from the statistical distribution of the variables involved in the potential estimation in the form of standard deviations. They are assessed for various modelling steps and combined to obtain an uncertainty on the PV potential. The steps of this method include the physical potential, driven by the horizontal solar radiation, the geographic potential, accounting for the impact of the built environment, and the technical potential, defined as the potential electricity generation.

10.2.4 Alpine

Schwarz 2022 [75]:

To evaluate the role of alpine PV plants for the Swiss power system, scenarios were developed using the Nexus-e modelling platform. To consider alpine PVA in the scenarios, a GIS dataset on feasible PV installation areas in the alpine region and a dataset with spatial electricity generation from PVA (Sunwell model) were used. The combination of these two datasets (feasible PV installation area per node [m^2] and normalized electricity generation per area [kW/m^2]) yields the maximum technical potential for electricity generation in the alpine area.

Remund et al. 2019 [19]:

No information about the methodology.

De Ferrars 2023 [33]:

A combination of GIS and MultiCriteria Decision-Making methods (MCDM) is used to find the optimal placement of PV solar facilities. Extensive cartographic and alphanumeric databases can be created. With MCDM applied to the databases, problems can then be solved in a simplified way and different criteria can be defined.

Meyer et al. 2023 [32]

Meteotest has developed a GIS tool to determine suitable locations in the Swiss Alpine region. Maps in 100 m resolution of the mean monthly values of the horizontal global irradiation are used. At 46 test sites calculated with Meteonorm, the correlations between the horizontal irradiation and the electricity production of the vertical modules were developed. Areas with minimum irradiation as well as technically (e.g. forest, poor subsoil, avalanches), politically (e.g. construction zone, airports, protected areas), socially (e.g. ski areas, golf courses), economically (development through infrastructure) unusable areas were excluded.

10.2.5 Lakes

Wanner et al. 2022 [28]:

No information about the methodology.

10.2.6 Agri-PV

Jäger et al. 2022 [29]:

For the calculation of the geographical potential, the construction zone and a buffer of 1 km around the construction zone are considered with the help of GIS data. From this area, the three types of open arable land or crop rotation area, permanent grassland and permanent crops are determined. If exclusion criteria are considered, further areas are omitted because they are classified by the federal government as worthy of protection. A further step is the categorisation of areas from the solar irradiation with ArcGIS. It is assumed that only areas with an average solar irradiation of 1100 kWh/m² and more per year are suitable for agri-PV at all. The solar irradiation in 2021 was calculated using an elevation model with a spatial resolution of 25 m. The remaining areas were then categorised according to their solar irradiation. For the remaining areas, the potential was calculated as 735 MWh/ha/a (arable), 293 MWh/ha/a (permanent green) and 862 MWh/ha/a (permanent crops).

Anderegg et al. 2024 [30]:

When calculating the geographical potential, the construction zone and a buffer of 1 km around the construction zone are taken into account with the help of Meteonorm. The agricultural areas within this perimeter are taken into account. The resulting areas are assigned a management status. These are "open arable land", "permanent grassland", "permanent crops", "protected cultivation", "summering areas" and "biodiversity areas (BFF)". The last two are not considered further. A further step is the categorisation of the areas based on solar radiation. It is assumed that only areas with an average solar radiation of 1000 kWh/m² and more per year are suitable (Meteonorm with 100m grid). Areas with overriding national conservation interests are also excluded. The PV yield is then determined using reference systems for the various crops and the assumptions from the feasibility study [29].

10.2.7 Others

Nordmann et al. 2012 [34]:

The theoretical PV potential is the total realisable PV power without considering technical conditions of the components or economic/time factors. The technical potential describes the share of the theoretical potential that can be used with technically real options available on the market. Limitations due to typical market components are considered. Non-technical restrictions on the use of LSW for PV systems are not considered. With the further development of PV technology, new developments of technologies and the expected price reduction of PV systems, a distinction can be made between the PV systems that make the most sense in the short term and systems that can be realised at a later point in time. This creates a temporal staggering. The developable potential reflects the expected actual contribution of the use of photovoltaics. In addition, non-technical factors are considered. Psychological factor: acceptance of the population, Political factor: political framework conditions. The radiation map from Meteotest is used for the irradiation and the MISTRA LBK is used for the noise barriers.

Grüter et al. 2021 [35]:

Interviews were conducted with key stakeholders (operators/investors, authorities, developers, associations) to identify opportunities and challenges for the different categories. Based on the interviews with various experts and the research conducted, the infrastructure categories were evaluated with respect to the parameters mentioned and the potential for PV was estimated. For some infrastructure categories, the regulatory environment is crucial, which was therefore specifically considered and included in the evaluation.

Remund et al. 2019 [19]:

For the area of roads, free areas along national roads and parking lots a reduction of 25-99 % was performed. Further information about the method is not available.

Planair SA 2021 [36]:

For the calculation of the potential for road and rail, installation configurations were determined that consider the constraints according to a realistic scenario. The Annex of the report with the calculation method cannot be found.

Meier 2023 [37]:

The "ArcGIS Pro Version 3.0.3" software is used for the spatial analysis. The topographical landscape model of Switzerland and the irradiation data of a typical meteorological year are used to determine the theoretical solar power production on car parks. The "swissTLM3D" data set contains all public and private car parks with at least 25 or 50 parking spaces. A distance of 5 meters from buildings and plot boundaries is applied and the cantonally defined forest distance is observed. Additionally there must be at least four car parks next to each other. The result is a usage factor of 0.9. However, if only the parking lots are covered, a usage factor of 0.43 is expected.

10.2.8 Additional studies

Bartlett et al. 2018 [44]:

The satellite-derived irradiation data from MeteoSwiss are used together with considerations for clouds and topography shading. The PV panel placement was weighted proportionately to population density and there are no calculations on how much area is potentially available. It is simply assumed that a sufficient number of PV panels are installed to cover the deficit resulting when removing nuclear power plants.

Kahl et al. 2019 [52]:

The required area to produce 12 TWh/a was calculated depending on the inclination of the modules and the location (urban, mountains and mountains without snow). The calculations were performed with the SUNWELL model.

Dujardin et al. 2021 [60]:

The hourly spatially explicit electricity production of PV panels and wind turbines is calculated using the SUNWELL model on a 1.6×2.3 km grid and the wind fields of the numerical weather

prediction model COSMO-1 on a 1.1 km grid. The site-specific tilt and azimuth of each PV panel are chosen to maximise winter production. The potential for installing PV panels was calculated using a GIS analysis (resolution 50 m). The maximum installed PV panel area corresponds to 5 % of the available area.